

Alcohol Detection with Vehicle Warning

*Lindelwa Mazitshana **Ali M A Almaktoof

Department of Electrical, Electronics and Computer engineering
Cape Peninsula University of Technology
Symphony Way, Bellville, Cape Town, 7535

*Lindelwa.mazitshana@gmail.com, **almaktoofa@cput.ac.za

Abstract- It takes being alive and healthy to tackle challenges for sustainable development. The source of drinking and driving has led to loss of life and properties. Control measures to ensure drivers are not under influence of alcohol while driving such as Blood Alcohol Content (BAC) check remains unrealizable due to used personnel, equipment and maintenance cost involved. A less consuming effort has been proposed using MQ3 gas sensor mounted on the steering wheel, powered by ignition of the vehicle to detect alcohol processed by Arduino Uno. In this project an Arduino Uno compares output with set threshold for compliance. If threshold is exceeded four modules are simultaneously triggered. Fuel supply control module is activated by a relay to cut-off engine and bring vehicle to stationary. The Liquid Cristal Display (LCD) module display is activated to show alcohol has been detected. The Global Positioning System (GPS) module is activated to detect exact location co-ordinates. The Global System for Mobile (GSM) module is activated to send notice on LCD display and location co-ordinates to subject's next of keen for immediate attention.

Key words- Alcohol Detection; Arduino Uno; Drink driving; GPS; GSM module; MQ3 gas sensor

I. INTRODUCTION

Road safety is a major social concern around the world especially South Africa. Drinking and driving is already a serious public health problem which is likely to emerge as one of the problems in the near future [1]. The proposed project aims at reducing road accidents due to drunk driving. So if a driver is drunk and tries to drive the system will analyse their breath, if alcohol is detected engine will be locked hindering vehicle from starting and sends location with vehicle information to next of keen of the driver. In another case if the driver starts drinking while already driving, sensor will still detect the smell of alcohol and stop engine. This project uses Arduino Uno, GSM module, GPS module with MQ3 sensor and DC motors. Alcohol sensor constantly monitors drivers' breath and sends signals to Arduino Uno.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Hardware modules

The entire system adopted the Arduino Uno microcontroller board. The Arduino is the central unit of the system, all components are interfaced to the board and programmed according to their functionality to operate in synchronization. [2]

Figure 1. System flow chart

III. EXPERIMENTATION

B. Simulation

Figure 2. Proteus used to simulate parts of the system

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Below results were observed when GSM,GPS and MQ3 sensor were interfaced. I still need to control motors.

Figure 3. Results after alcohol was detected

Lindy is too drunk to drive :
Lat: 34.025002 Long:
18.411001

Figure 4. Results sent to next of keen with co-ordinates

V. CONCLUSIONS

The whole system has advantage of small volume and more reliability, it improves the safety of human being and hence providing effective development to reduce accidents due to drunk drivers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Existing System Alcohol Breathalysers, Internet:(<https://www.towardszero.vic.gov.au/news/articles/TAC-encourages-people-to-separate-drinking-and-driving>) [May, 30, 2018].
- [2] “**Global Status report** on Road Safety for 2015" Global road deaths based on an article dated on this day 2015-12-01 [on-line]. Available:http://mobile.24.com/?p=minisite_motorng [Mar.04, 2018].
- [3] RD Blomberg, R C Peck, M Burns, and D Fiorentino. Crash risk of alcohol involved driving: A case-control study. Technical report, Dunlap & Associates Inc., Stamford CT, 2005.

Author Biographical Statements

Lindelwa Mazitshana obtained her Diploma in 2015 from the Department of Electrical Electronics and Computer Engineering at CPUT. She is currently busy with BTech in the same field.

Ali M. Almaktoof was born in Libya in 1978. He received the B. Eng. from Al-Tahady University, Libya in 2001 and M.Sc. from University of Tripoli, Libya in 2008, and DTech from CPUT in 2015 all in electrical engineering. He is currently a lecturer in the Department of electrical, electronic and computer engineering at CPUT in South Africa. He is a full member of Institution of Engineering and Technology (IET) and World Society of Sustainable Energy Technology (WSSET). He is an active member of the Centre of Distributed Power and Electronics Systems and Energy Institute at CPUT. Dr Almaktoof research interests include control of power converters, predictive control, multilevel converters and renewable energy systems applications.